

IPBES IAS assessment, data management report for Chapter 6. Assessing invasive alien species governance options

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Description:

Chapter 6 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control provides insights on the governance options pertaining to IAS control scoping in the past, present and future. To comprehend global governance alternatives, challenges, efficacy and future scope for dealing with IAS, we systematically reviewed published scientific knowledge on Web of Science. Our review questions were 1) What are the range of alternative governance response options for dealing with IAS? 2) What are the challenges facing IAS governance? 3) What evidence is available on effective IAS governance options? and 4) What governance options are available for transformative progress towards meeting IAS goals?

Process overview:

Protocol:

- Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic Review
 - Search language(s): English
 - Search terms: governance AND [alien OR exotic OR non-indigenous OR non-native OR invasi*] AND species
 - Search engine: Web of Science, Google Scholar
 - Date: 17th March 2020
 - Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.)
- 1) Fields extracted: Title, Authors, Abstract, Published year, Journal, Volume, Issue, Page numbers, DOI.

2) Assessment fields (options assigned under it): IAS specific (yes, no); Governance mode (hierarchical, science and technology, strategic behavior, adapt-collaborate, multiple); Study type (empirical, review, systematic review, meta-analysis, commentary/overview, policy analysis, other); Locality (Africa, Americas, Antarctica, Asia-Pacific, Europe and Central Asia, Ocean, Global, Multiple, General); Priority focus (species, pathways, areas, multiple, other, n/a); Levels of governance (global, multi-national, national, sub-national, regional, local, other, multiple); Environment (terrestrial, freshwater, marine, island, polar, mountain, marine and freshwater, other, multiple); Invasion stage (transport, introduction, establishment, spread, impact, multiple, n/a); Actors (government, civil society, IPLC, research, education, corporate, NGOs, other, multiple, IAS managers, Challenges (complexity, uncertainty, information availability-flow-access, traditional governance, fragmentation, externality, implementation, collective action, awareness and perception); Governance options (co-operation and co-management, communication, coordination, stakeholder participation, resourcing, enabling policy environment, adaptive management and organizational structures, understand complex natural and socio-ecological systems, build capacity, knowledge integration and access, power balance and legitimized knowledge, strategic thinking about governance system best suited to the context, other).

- Results:

Figure: Percent of the total studies categorized (n = 92) under different alternatives in every aspect of IAS governance option (Governance type, Level of governance, IPBES region, Actors, Invasion stage, Environment, Taxonomic groups)

- File:

List of literatures_IAS_DMR_Ch6_ver1.txt = List of all papers, references and details of reviewer